

5G experimentation environment for third party media services: the 5GMediaHUB project

Apostolos Siokis, Kostas Ramantas
Iquadrat Informatica S.L
Barcelona, Spain
{a.siokis, kramantas}@iquadrat.com

George Margetis
*Institute of Computer Science, Foundation
for Research and Technology Hellas*
Heraklion, Greece
gmarget@ics.forth.gr

Constantine Stephanidis
*Institute of Computer Science,
Foundation for Research and
Technology Hellas)*
*Department of Computer Science,
University of Crete*
Heraklion, Greece
cs@ics.forth.gr

Loizos Christofi
eBOS Technologies Ltd
Nicosia, Cyprus
loizos.christofi@ebos.com.cy

Kostis Tzanettis
*Appart AE New Technologies Computer and
Telecommunications*
Athens, Greece
k.tzanettis@app-art.gr

Håkon Lønsethagen
Telenor Research, Telenor
Norway
hakon.lonsethagen@telenor.com

Ioannis Markopoulos
*Elliniki Etairia Tilepikoinonion kai
Tilematikon Efarmogon AE (Forthnet)*
Athens, Greece
jmarkopo@forthnet.gr

Luis Sanabria-Russo, Hatim Chergui,
Christos Verikoukis
*Telecommunications Technological Centre
of Catalonia (CTTC/CERCA)*
Castelldefels, Spain
{luis.sanabria, hatim.chergui,
cveri}@cttc.es

Abstract—5G is expected to account for a large portion of the global mobile industry over the following years. The media vertical sector is expected to be one of the leading adopters of 5G technology, due to its 100x faster gigabit-per-second speeds, ultra-low latencies and higher-reliability compared to 4G connectivity, as media mobile app developers can truly push the boundaries on features and functionality in any novel mobile application. However, 5G networks present challenges (such as security and privacy issues, setup of viable 5G-based mobile app business models, testing and verification issues) to media application developers. To address the above needs and challenges 5GMediaHUB aims to build and operate an elastic, secure, trusted, all-in-one, multi-tenant service execution and NetApps development environment based on an open cloud-based architecture and APIs, by developing and integrating a testing and validation system with existing well-established 5G testbeds, for enabling the fast prototyping, testing and validation of novel 5G media services and NetApps, thus reducing the entry barrier to 3rd party media application testers (from SMEs, service providers, researchers, etc.).

Keywords—5G; experimentation testbeds; netapps; network slicing

I. INTRODUCTION

The media vertical sector is expected to be one of the leading adopters of 5G technology. 5G will offer unprecedented opportunities to capitalize on the capabilities of a new breed of applications that entail fast ultra-high-resolution video (4k/8k) streaming with high frame rates, Augmented Reality (AR), Virtual Reality (VR) and Extended Reality (XR), 360o immersiveness, and more, offering a more

realistic, more reliable and improved user experience. However, along with the opportunities and benefits, 5G networks also present some key challenges to media application developers.

Therefore, there's the need to provide a 5G-based secure and trusted experimentation playground through which media mobile app developers would have the opportunity to test and validate their applications in an integrated, open and cost-efficient manner, so as to remove operational uncertainties and reduce market entry barriers prior to being ported and deployed in industrial public 5G networks. To address the above needs and challenges and realize its vision, 5GMediaHUB will create a high-level abstraction layer between media applications and the underlying 5G infrastructure, enabling them to have a simplified but sufficient abstracted visibility (i.e. view of the network corresponding to a specific network slice) of the infrastructure state for network-wide control and resource management, so as to be able to dynamically deploy, orchestrate and manage their services through elastic network slicing, to ensure service and workload isolation. This will subsequently provide tenants with a flexible and cost-efficient way to support their applications by providing access to 5G network resources. Leveraging the NFV Infrastructures of the 5GMediaHUB 5G-PPP testbeds in Oslo (i.e. TNOR's 5G-VINNI [1]) and in Spain (i.e. CTTC's 5G testbed in Barcelona [2]), 5GMediaHUB will offer "Platform as a Service" (PaaS) capabilities via a set of open-standards Northbound APIs provided by a corresponding set of application enablement services, termed NetApps. These include both vertical-

specific media NetApps and vertical-agnostic NetApps, hosted in a NetApps Repository, which supports uploading 3rd party media NetApps or even NetApps from other vertical domains.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows: Section II presents the 5GMediaHUB experimentation facility architecture. Section III describes the Deep Neural Networks approach that will be followed for dynamic end-to-end slice management. Section IV outlines the Development and Continuous Integration DevOps workflows that will be followed in the project. Section V is about the QoE (Quality of Experience) in 5G networks based on SDN and NFV. Section VI deals with the security framework applied using software defined perimeters in 5G and section VII is about the NetApps and Northbound APIs. Section VIII concludes the paper.

II. 5GMEDIAHUB EXPERIMENTATION FACILITY HIGH-LEVEL ARCHITECTURE

5GMediaHUB Experimentation Facility offers an elastic, trusted and secure service execution environment based on an open-standards cloud-based architecture and APIs, supporting multi-tenancy. This will provide 3rd party application developers, such as SMEs, media content and service providers, and NetApps developers, who may not have access to 5G testbed infrastructures, the opportunity to experiment, test and validate their media applications under realistic conditions thus significantly reducing any uncertainties before actual commercial service deployment. The main elements of the 5GMediaHUB’s architecture (Fig. 1) are:

The Application layer, which hosts the 3rd party media applications. 5GMediaHUB will implement the new ETSI MEC PaaS extensions for the first time, supporting containerized and VM based workloads. Cloud-native vertical applications are implemented as a mesh of containerized microservices that can be defined with state-of-the-art Container Management Frameworks (e.g. Docker

in a 5G test environment to ensure their proper operation, and remove any uncertainties prior to wide-scale deployment. Furthermore, it offers scheduling, validation, verification, analytics and QoS/QoE monitoring mechanisms to experimenters. The 5GMediaHUB experimentation tools are structured in an innovative DevOps environment, to allow seamless test scheduling and execution via DevOps pipelines.

The NetApps & slice (abstraction) layer, which offers PaaS capabilities to 3rd party vertical application developers, abstracting the underlying NFVI and facilitating rapid prototyping and cross-platform interoperability. 5GMediaHUB will implement NetApps that cater to the media industry, which will be hosted in a NetApp Repository. NetApp VNF chains are implemented via Network Slice Instances (NSIs) that can span across multiple NFVIs and testbed facilities.

The 5G infrastructure layer, which consists of 5G testbed facilities. In 5GMediaHUB two well-established 5G testbeds, i.e. TNOR’s Oslo 5G testbed from 5G-VINNI ICT-17 project and CTTC’s 5G testbed from 5G-SOLUTIONS ICT-19 and MonB5G ICT-20 projects are used and extended to provide the 5G network capabilities. The two 5G testbeds will be interconnected via the GEANT network, and cross-domain slicing will be achieved through the open source WAN Infrastructure Management (WIM) plugin of the ETSI OSM contributed by METRO-HAUL project.

The UE layer, which is a unique feature of 5GMediaHUB, consists of a farm of UEs to enable the end-to-end testing of a wide variety of media applications. The UE farm includes (i) 5G enabled remotely controlled smartphone devices or similarly spec’d clusters of Single Board Computers (e.g. Raspberry Pis) with 5G USB modems that can execute tests encapsulated in Docker Containers; (ii) locally controlled UEs, such as 4k/8k video cameras, 4k/8k TV sets, immersive (AR/VR/XR) headsets that will be controlled by the 5G testbed owners on behalf of the experimenters. In the UE layer handover selection algorithms (e.g., [3], [4]) will also be explored.

The Security Framework, which implements secure user authorization and authentication, software defined perimeter (SDP) protection and isolation via dedicated network slices. 5GMediaHUB will be the first concrete attempt of SDP integration with 5G infrastructures.

III. DYNAMIC END-TO-END SLICE MANAGEMENT BASED ON DEEP NEURAL NETWORKS

5G Network slicing has emerged as one of the hottest topics in 5G research, as it deals with efficient splitting of physical network resources into multiple virtual networks (i.e. slices) that aim to optimally satisfy a diverse range of application QoS requirements. Ensuring that each network slice is isolated from all other slices is an important characteristic so as to ensure that traffic on one slice does not “bleed” into other slices. Since slices are isolated, it is imperative that they are allocated sufficient resources to meet expectations of QoS. Hence, being able to predict resource demand is critical to the efficient design, construction, deployment, operation and management of network slices [5]. Such predictions require analysis and processing of an enormous amount of data, which is beyond human capacity given real-time requirements. Hence, the proliferation of Machine Learning and Deep Learning (ML/DL) algorithms has lent itself toward realizing autonomous ‘cognitive

Fig. 1. 5GMediaHUB Experimentation Facility high-level architecture

Compose, Kubernetes Helm, etc.). Media Applications will leverage the NetApps’ Northbound APIs to interact with the underlying NetApps in a plug-and-play NFVI agnostic manner.

The Experimentation Tools layer, which allows the validation and optimization of their services and applications

network management' [6], e.g. capitalizing on ML superior capacity to analyze, identify patterns and anticipate future events toward realizing "self-aware, self-configuring, self-optimization, self-healing and self-protecting" networks. Once slices are created however, application-awareness becomes critical, as different application types require different network characteristics. In this respect, the network needs to monitor the application's condition in real time, so as to infer the proper resource isolation to guarantee enhanced performance, as well as QoS. AI/ML approaches have started gaining significant traction among various application tracks in SDN and NFV based networks [7], and their application for dynamic slice management is a relatively new concept, that has been emphasized as a key enabler for automating 5G network slicing functions. A logical next step would be to integrate cognitive network management with fine-grained application detection so as to: (i) optimize network slices for specific application types; and (ii) configure the slice resource management for a specific application in real-time so as to best fulfill that application's requirements. Towards (i), the employment of vanilla deep learning structures for dynamic optimization of network slices has been employed in some approaches [8], [9], while another approach [10] notably experimented with a dedicated, data analytics tool, specifically designed for network capacity prediction. Generic approaches to network slicing optimization strategies, where the strategies are encoded instead of resource schedules have also been explored [11]. Towards (ii) on the other hand, application classification via ML-based traffic classification and crowdsourcing has been proposed as early as 2013 [12], while recent frameworks incorporate ML-based approaches tailored for QoE, by monitoring the application's condition via the training of the data from both Northbound and Southbound Interfaces [13]. For multimedia services, application awareness is critical for predicting user mobility, determining proper video encoding schemes and allow video segment caching by leveraging on MEC so as to guarantee QoE in challenging scenarios [14].

5GMediaHUB will pursue rigorous integration of densely connected, multiscale Deep Neural Networks into cognitive network management processes, incorporating a significantly higher number of media-related parameters in its models than SoTA (State-of-The-Art) works. An explicit design and training process will be leveraged to address the specific needs of the media sector, so as to deliver optimal media content, traffic pattern identification and highly accurate prediction of resource demands that will drive the 5G slicing strategy. Specifically, Deep Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) and short-term memory (LSTM) methods will be considered for integration into the CDSO Slicing Manager module, to drive the cognitive management of slice resources that underpin NetApps. To train the Deep CNN models, their loss function will be fed with media specific QoS (Quality of Service) / QoE (Quality of Experience) KPIs (Key Performance Indicators) from the Continuous QoS/QoE Monitoring Engine, so as to dynamically re-distribute slice resources. Hence, instead of training to merely predict traffic, 5GMediaHUB will change the objective and train for predicting NetApps KPIs (e.g., Frame Loss Ratio, MOS score, delay, stall events, etc.) and SLA compliance. Furthermore, domain-specific traffic forecasting and dynamic slice reconfiguration is expected to significantly reduce the needs for resource over-provisioning, minimizing operating expenses. The 5GMediaHUB Experimentation Facility will

serve as a playground to optimally train CNN models for all media related use-cases addressed by 5GMediaHUB (i.e. video streaming, entertainment, VR/AR/XR) for the first time.

IV. DEVOPS EXPERIMENTATION AND SERVICE VALIDATION

DevOps unifies the development and operation of service to reap the synergetic benefits and is of great importance in satisfying 5G networks' demand for faster service delivery within complex environments. As indicated by a whitepaper [15] released by Nokia, only 32% of investigated network operators have plans to use DevOps in 2020, and DevOps is only slowly extending into 5G compared with the adoption in cloud and data centre environments. Under 5G-PPP, the 5G-TANGO project aimed at the significant challenges associated with both the development and deployment of the complex services envisioned for 5G networks, and developed an extended NFV DevOps model between service developers, telecom operators and vertical industries, increasing operational efficiency, facilitating the implementation and validation of new services and accelerating the adoption of NFV technologies. On the other hand, 5G-Media, another 5G-PPP Phase 2 project aimed at innovating media-related applications by investigating how these applications and underlying 5G networks should be coupled and interwork to the benefit of both, to ensure the proper resource allocation for applications while maintaining smooth traffic in 5G networks. Finally, the SONATA orchestrator [16] supports a DevOps workflow, which implies continuous deployment and integration during service development. The aforementioned projects lay a solid foundation for the DevOps in 5G, but not enough emphasis has been put on the operations and continuous performance monitoring of services. Another limitation is the lack of formal Validation and Verification (V&V), which is a critical requirement of the growing marketplaces for NFV products and is currently addressed by the OPNFV Dovetail project. There is no silver bullet for service development and deployment, and experience learnt from the automated deployment and testing should be keeping fed back to the DevOps process for the 3rd party media application developers and the experiment tools to achieve continuous performance improvements. Currently, DevOps has just been partially executed since testing results are not thoroughly analyzed and utilized for DevOps.

5GMediaHUB will meaningfully extend previous efforts that focused on Development and Continuous Integration DevOps workflows by adding support for Operations, Administration and Management (OAM). Specifically, the 5GMediaHUB Experimentation Facility will support continuous QoS and QoE monitoring, allowing 3rd party media applications developers and experimenters to qualify and verify their applications and NetApps with a familiar set of tools that they already use in their production environments. 5GMediaHUB will hide the complexity of service development, deployment, as well as Validation and Verification (V&V) via predefined Continuous Integration (CI) and Continuous Delivery (CD) pipelines for automated functional testing, performance testing, validation/verification of KPIs, and QoS / QoE qualification. Furthermore, tests will be administered via a user-friendly sequential process by filling-in the different attributes for composing experiments (e.g. experiment scheduling, resource reservation, etc.) which is authorized by 5G facility owners.

Finally, 5GMediaHUB will incorporate a centrally managed “UE farm” in its infrastructure, allowing experimenters to deploy tests directly at UEs, thus considering the impact of the RAN (Radio Access Network).

V. 5G NETWORKS BASED ON SDN AND NFV

QoS and QoE are at the core of the 3GPP R.16 Media Streaming (5GMS [17]) specifications, which define a Media Session Handling API towards the 5GMSd Application Function (AF) to be used for QoE reporting, policy enforcement and charging. The 5GMSd communicates with the Policy Control Function (PCF), which is configured with the corresponding QoS parameters and charging information. However, the exact QoE mechanisms and Video Quality Assessment (VQA) metrics to be implemented are not specified. VQA metrics can be classified as subjective, that rely on human quality assessment to compute a Mean Opinion Score (MOS), and objective, that typically rely on perception models to predict human quality assessment. The latter include Full-Reference (FR) schemes, such as Netflix’s VMAF [18] and Reduced-Reference (RR) schemes, such as SpEEDQA [19], etc. More advanced approaches leverage AI/ML techniques to predict the MOS score [20]. For the optimization of video QoE, which is quantified via the aforementioned VQA metrics, several SDN and NFV mechanisms have been proposed. An SDN-based bandwidth broker solution has been proposed [21] for improving per-session and per-group QoE metrics via HTTP adaptive streaming (HAS). Bandwidth allocation per video stream is modelled as a convex optimization problem, which relies on a concave network utility maximization function and also addresses fairness. A programmable QoE-SDN APP [22] has been introduced which takes advantage of state information exposed by the SDN controller (e.g. data rates of mobile users), in order to trade-off stalling events with lower HAS video bit rates, since the former have a much stronger QoE impact. An SDN-controlled dynamic routing scheme [23] has been proposed to interconnect video clients with the optimal video cache. Q-FDBA dynamic bandwidth allocation algorithm based on reinforcement learning has been proposed [24] with a focus on fairness optimization. Finally, data-driven QoE optimization for 5G networks is being standardized by the ETSI ENI group, and showcased via the Application Characteristic based Network Operation (ACNO) use case [25]. Current SoTA QoE optimization schemes in the literature are typically evaluated in simulated and emulated environments (e.g. Mininet), and they do not take into account the intricacies and APIs (e.g. Media Session Handling API) of the 5G core.

5GMediaHUB will implement its QoE engines in a real-world 5G experimentation environment. The 5G Streaming NetApp will offer QoE support out of the box, leveraging the Media Session Handling API of the 5G Core as well as the CDSO and SDN APIs to optimize HTTP Adaptive Streaming. Thus, the video quality of clients will be derived on-the-fly by the NetApp based on network and service KPI, predicting their impact on QoE and signalling graceful degradation, if and when required, to prevent stalling events. Advanced Deep Learning (DL) techniques, and in particular, Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs) will be leveraged to implement data-driven QoE in accordance with the ETSI ENI ACNO specifications. These will automatically select the key features that affect QoE and train models that implement multi-objective optimization. 5GMediaHUB offers the

unique capability to measure QoE directly at the UE level via its centrally managed UE farm infrastructure, hence deriving a much more objective score that also takes into account the impact of the RAN on video quality.

VI. SECURITY FRAMEWORK APPLIED USING SOFTWARE DEFINED PERIMETERS IN 5G NETWORKS

Application Centric Infrastructures and Cloud-Native principles are rapidly making conventional security approaches, such as Perimeter Firewalls, insufficient or even obsolete. Conventional security appliances, as well as their virtualized equivalents, generally rely on topological information (e.g., service placement at individual hypervisors) which are often stale, as modern containerized applications react instantly to varying workloads [26] and VNF placement is generally decoupled from network topology. 5G further complicates the consistent security policy enforcement (e.g., related to ACL Segmentation, Data Encryption) with its multi-domain and multi-tenant infrastructures. This is partially mitigated with the introduction of the API Exposing Function (AEF), which was defined as part of the CAPIF specifications to provide secure access to the Northbound interfaces of internal services. However, this solution still has a very limited flexibility, and follows an “all-or-nothing” approach. Software Defined Perimeter (SDP) technology overcomes the aforementioned limitations by creating dynamic micro-perimeters for each authenticated user. Endpoints and hosts attempting to access a given resource are pre-authenticated and pre-authorized before they are granted access to the infrastructure and any resource within it. SDPs are a secure enclave of authenticated participants, where authorization is controlled via a trust broker (i.e. SDP Controller). The resources inside the perimeter are invisible to unauthenticated third parties (“black cloud” concept) thus substantially reducing the attack surface. Furthermore, instead of providing full access inside the security perimeter (as is the case with traditional Network Access Control (NAC) security), SDP adopts a zero-trust model, and admits access to specific resources, as defined by the security policy. SDP has demonstrated success in military security and its scalability has been proven by very large global corporations, e.g. Google [27] and Coca Cola [28]. The SDP architecture consists of Controllers and Hosts: The SDP Hosts can either initiate or accept connections that are managed by interactions with the SDP Controller via a separate control channel. SDP has been tested in world-scale hackathons for DDoS attacks, credential theft, Advanced Persistent Threats, malware and other attacks (>1 billion server exploits and DDoS attacks launched from 104 countries), with not a single successful network-based and lateral-movement attacks and no data loss so far [29]. A recent study [30], highlighted SDP as one of the top technologies for information security and although SDP’s low penetration in the market [31], it predicts that by 2021, 60% of enterprises [32] will phase out traditional NAC-based security and network VPNs in favour of SDP.

Despite its emerging popularity in the industry, there is virtually non-existent prior work on SDP integration with 5G infrastructures. 5GMediaHUB will integrate SDP in 5G NFVIs (Network Function Virtualization Infrastructure) with PaaS capabilities for the first time, allowing vertical applications, 5G internal services and 5G Core functions to share NFVI resources with unprecedented granularity. Specifically, highly sensitive NetApps and 5G Application Functions can be deployed alongside 3rd party services sharing the same hypervisor, but will be invisible to each other. This goes beyond the existing 3GPP specifications, that introduce a fixed perimeter between internal and external resources that is implementable with physical segmentation of resources and the AEF function as an API gateway that securely exposes internal APIs. 5GMediaHUB follows a different approach (Fig. 2) with the AEF acting as an SDP Initiating Host (IH) that forwards API requests to the NetApps inside the perimeter via the Dynamic Tunnel Mode, ensuring that the internal APIs (and exposed networking ports) remain invisible outside the perimeter. Finally, 5GMediaHUB will adopt and extend the Slicing Trust Management Module from the MonB5G project, to implement AI/ML based malicious traffic pattern detection mechanisms, ensuring slice security and isolation. This module will be combined with the SDP mechanisms to identify security incidents as they happen (e.g., individual compromised hosts or 3rd party vertical services) and immediately revoke their access to Northbound APIs (e.g. invalidating their client certificates) and perimeters.

Fig. 2. 5GMediaHUB Security Framework

VII. NETAPPS AND NORTHBOUND APIS

The 5G Service-Based Architecture (SBA [33]) was designed from the ground up to serve vertical industries in addition to end users, while several initiatives for the enablement of verticals in future 5G networks are underway by the 3GPP SA6. In the 5G SBA the Control Plane was separated from the user plane for increased efficiency, hence 5G vertical applications can be divided at the “Application Service” (AS) and “Application Function” (AF) logical entities. For example, in the 3GPP R.16 Media Streaming (5GMS [17]) specifications, the streaming functionality is divided in the Media AS and Media AF components. A PDU session is established from the UE media application client to the Media AS, which is hosted inside the telco Data Network. The Media AF issues control plane requests to the 5G core Network Functions on behalf of the Media AS (e.g., to the Policy Control Function, or PCF) to ensure QoS and QoE. As

per the 5G SBA, control plane NFs and AFs interact via standardized Service Based Interfaces (SBIs). It follows that 3rd party vertical application development is extremely challenging and very sensitive in nature due to the interaction with 5G APIs that require a high level of trust to access. Thus, 3GPP R.15 introduced a Common API Framework (CAPIF) for verticals, focusing on common aspects of Northbound APIs that apply to all services, such as registration, discovery, event reporting, identity management and billing, and securely exposing capabilities of the 5G Network. Furthermore, 3GPP R.16 TS 23.434 specifies a Service Enabler Architecture Layer for Verticals (SEAL [34]) that implement the aforementioned CAPIF APIs, while more Northbound APIs can be implemented by dedicated SEAL services per vertical application domain (e.g., Media, V2X, etc.). These Northbound APIs can be reused by multiple vertical applications (or VAL services as per 3GPP’s terminology), greatly simplifying their development and deployment. It is evident that 3GPP’s approach for large scale 3rd party vertical development is in-line with the ETSI MEC ISG PaaS enhancements (currently still in a draft state), however no study has been performed for the mapping between ETSI MEC PaaS extensions and the 3GPP SEAL architecture, or to address multi-domain scenarios (e.g., 5G infrastructures with multiple facilities, MEC nodes, etc.). Finally, SEAL services for the Media industry have not yet been defined, while it is clear that 3GPP foresees innovation mainly from VAL service providers, delegating the development of SEAL services and Control Plane Application Functions to telecom operators, and their trusted vendors.

5GMediaHUB’s ambition is to go beyond 3GPP specifications, offering PaaS capabilities and abstracting 5G and NFV complexities from vertical application providers via media specific NetApps. 5GMediaHUB will implement NetApps for the media industry adopting the 3GPP SEAL architecture and ensuring compliance with the ETSI MEC ISG PaaS extensions for the first time. Furthermore, going beyond SEAL specifications, 5GMediaHUB NetApps will combine AF and AS VNFs within Network Slice Instances (NSIs), which will be deployed and orchestrated by the 5GMediaHUB CDSO in cross-domain scenarios. NetApps resources within NSSIs, can be shared by multiple vertical applications, hence avoiding the costly resource reservation and VNF instantiation for each vertical application deployment, increasing the ecosystem flexibility, decreasing costs and significantly decreasing service creation time. Moreover, while 3GPP has only foreseen large-scale 3rd party contributions in the form of vertical applications only, 5GMediaHUB’s open source NetApps repository based on Git SCM, will promote innovation and collaborative development of Control Plane and User Plane VNFs, such that 3rd parties can also participate in the development of telco’s PaaS infrastructures. It is foreseen that only trusted 3rd parties that are vetted (and appropriately accredited) by the 5G network provider will have the rights to deploy Control Plane VNFs. Nevertheless, 5GMediaHUB’s innovative security framework will greatly simplify the definition of trust domains, that could vary from access to the Northbound APIs, to the deployment of User Plane and / or Control Plane VNFs. All NetApps and individual VNFs will be indexed by the NetApps Repository along with their metadata and interfaces, and will be searchable by 3rd parties that may easily create new NetApps combining existing VNFs with their own.

Finally, media vertical application developers will be able to search for applicable NetApps of their vertical domain and consume the NetApp Northbound APIs in their vertical applications in a developer friendly manner.

VIII. CONCLUSION

In this paper, the 5GMediaHUB key ambitions and goals have been presented, providing insight on key project activities to take place over the course of the next three years. 5GMediaHUB aims to enable EU to achieve its goal of becoming a world leader in 5G, by accelerating the testing and validation of innovative 5G-empowered media applications and NetApps from 3rd party experimenters and 3rd party NetApps developers, respectively, through an integrated, open and fully featured Experimentation Facility.

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